

Factors Affecting Utilization of Public Health Services for Noncommunicable Diseases in a Panchayath of Malappuram District, Kerala

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Abstract:

NCDs have a substantial impact on our community, and the government's health services are a cost-effective and efficient strategy to prevent and reduce the burden of NCDs. The identification of factors influencing the utilization of NCD clinics is critical for determining the gap between the goals of these programs and their implementation. It can be used to evaluate the efficacy of various strategies.

The aim of this study was to determine the percentage of people who prefer public sector NCD programmes along with the factors affecting the utilization of the same. in Malappuram, Kerala. Cross-sectional research of 100 people selected using multistage systematic random sampling was carried out in Kerala's Malappuram district. The obtained data were analysed using descriptive and analytical statistical approaches using Jamovi version 2.3.

NCDs are a major health burden in our society, and treating and preventing them is critical. Many factors influence the selection of health care facilities for chronic diseases, and the study found that education, occupation, awareness of government programs, distance to the health center, and insurance coverage all influenced these decisions. The cost of therapy also plays an important part in selecting a health care facility.

Keywords: Non-Communicable Diseases, Diabetes, Hypertension, Healthcare Utilisation, Healthcare Delivery.

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Introduction

Noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), also known as chronic diseases, tend to be of long duration and are the result of a combination of genetic, physiological, environmental and behavioral factors. The main types of NCD are cardiovascular diseases (such as heart attacks and stroke), cancers, chronic respiratory diseases (such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma) and diabetes. NCDs disproportionately affect people in low- and middle-income countries, where more than three quarters of global NCD deaths (31.4 million) occur. [1]. NCDs have significant impact over the life expectancy and productivity of a community. Increased prevalence of NCD had caused financial burden to the community. It can be tackled effectively by utilization of NCD preventive clinics provided by government health services. Under the National Programme for Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Diseases and Stroke (NPCDCS) now known as NPNCDC, (launched in 2010) as part of National Health Mission (NHM), The Department of Health & Family Welfare had launched several health programmes. The programme focuses on strengthening infrastructure,

human resource development, health promotion & awareness generation for prevention, early diagnosis, management and referral to an appropriate level of healthcare facility for treatment of the Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs). WHO under 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development recognizes NCDs as a major challenge for sustainable development. As part of the agenda, heads of state and government committed to develop ambitious national responses, by 2030, to reduce by one third premature mortality from NCDs through prevention and treatment. [2]

Noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) kill 41 million people each year, equivalent to 74% of all deaths globally. Each year, 17 million people die from a NCD before age 70; 86% of these premature deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries. [1]. According to the study report "India: Health of the Nation's States"- The India State-Level Disease Burden Initiative in 2017 by Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), it is estimated that the proportion of deaths due to Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) in India have increased from 37.9% in 1990 to 61.8% in 2016 [2]. In low-

resource settings, health-care costs for NCDs quickly drain household resources. The exorbitant costs of NCDs, including treatment, which is often lengthy and expensive, combined with loss of income, force millions of people into poverty annually and stifle development. The diagnosis, screening, and treatment of NCDs are all part of the management process, as is giving those who require palliative care access to it. A primary health care approach can be used to deliver high impact key NCD therapies, strengthening early identification and prompt treatment. Based on available data, early implementation of these measures can significantly lower the need for more costly medical care, making them attractive financial investments. [1]

Determining the variables influencing the use of NCD clinics is essential to evaluating the discrepancy between the goals of these initiatives and their implementation. It can be applied to evaluate these schemes' efficacy. The percentage of people who prefer public sector NCD programmes is to be estimated by this study along with the factors affecting the utilization of the same. This will support the creation of sufficient action plans for carrying out additional health programs. Since there isn't a comparable study being conducted among the study population right now, it will be helpful in determining the accessibility of health programs as well as the assessment of prevalent health conditions in the community.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: The current study was conducted as a cross-sectional study design so as to estimate the proportion/percentage of individuals utilizing NCD services (screening and treatment) in a selected geographical area (Puzhakattiri panchayath of Malappuram district)

Study setting and participants: The study was conducted in Puzhakattiri panchayath of Malappuram district which is the most populous district of Kerala state. The study participants were residents of Puzhakattiri panchayath who were above the age of 30 years.

Inclusion Criteria: participants aged 30 years and above residing at Puzhakattiri panchayath for at least 6 months and who are willing to participate.

Exclusion Criteria: Those who had any cognitive impairment.

Sample Size: According to study conducted in Kasargod, Kerala by C.K Bhagyalakshmi, Prakash Babu Kodali on Utilization of Noncommunicable Disease Services Provided by Public Health Facilities showed that over 34.67% have used NCD clinics [3]

Using the equation: $\frac{((1.96)^2 \times (p \times q))}{d \times d}$

$$p = 34.67$$

$$q = 100 - p$$

$$= 65.33$$

$$d = \text{absolute error } 9.5\% \text{ for confidence interval } 95\%$$

$$\text{Sample size, } n = Z^2 \frac{pq}{d^2}$$

for 95% Confidence interval,

$$Z = 1.96$$

$$n = 100$$

So, sample size will be 100

Sampling Method

The participants for the study were selected using multistage systematic random sampling. The first stage of sampling employed was a simple random sampling to select wards from the panchayath. Puzhakattiri panchayath has 17 wards, among these 4 wards were randomly selected by lottery method. For selecting 100 participants from these 4 wards systematic random sampling technique was used. As all the wards of the panchayat had approximately equal population size 25 each participant was selected from each ward. Each ward had minimum of 600 houses, 25 houses were selected from each ward using systematic random sampling technique. 24 was taken as sampling interval to choose houses. First house was selected randomly by lottery method. Available member of the house satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria were interviewed for data collection.

Methods:

Study Procedure- The patients were chosen from the Puzhakattiri panchayath by multistage systemic random sampling.

NCDs chosen for the study were

- i. Diabetes
- ii. Hypertension
- iii. Dyslipidemia
- iv. Coronary vascular diseases
- v. Cancer
- vi. Thyroid disease

Patients were interviewed regarding their health conditions, whether they were suffering from any of the above-mentioned disease conditions. They were asked about their treatment, compliance to medication, satisfaction, knowledge about government organized health programmes

Data Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using Jamovi version 3.2 software. The quantitative variables are summarized as mean with standard deviation. The statistical significance of association is tested using Pearson Chi square test for dichotomous variables.

Results

The study has included 100 participants using a multistage random sampling technique.

Socio-demographic details: The mean age of the study participants was found to be as 52.14± 8.24

years with maximum number of participants from the age group 51-60 years (39%) followed by age group 41-50 (33%). The study had 79% of the participants identified as males and rest as females. 89% of the families were of nuclear type and rest were joint families.

The current study had majority of population with completed higher secondary education (77%) and nearly half of the study population were unskilled and semiskilled workers.

Table 1: Socio-demographic variables of the study population

	Age Group	Frequency (%)
Age Group	36-40	1 (1%)
	41-50	33 (33%)
	51-60	39 (39%)
	61-70	27 (27%)
Gender	Female	21 (21%)
	Male	79 (79%)

Figure 1: Education status of the study population (n=100)

Figure 2: Occupation status of the study population (n=100)

Figure 3: Socio-economic status of the study population (n=100)

Understanding Patient Behavior and Preferences in Managing Non-Communicable Diseases: Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are a major health challenge worldwide, and understanding how individuals manage these conditions is crucial for improving public health strategies. This article examines various aspects of patient behavior and preferences related to the treatment and management of NCDs, based on recent survey data.

Medication Adherence and Healthcare Visits: One of the key findings from the study is the high rate of medication adherence among patients with NCDs. An overwhelming 98% of respondents reported that they are taking medication for their illness, while only 2% indicated that they are not on any medication. This suggests that most patients are actively managing their conditions with prescribed treatments.

Regular visits to healthcare centers are also common among the respondents, with 96% reporting that they visit a healthcare facility every month. Only 4% do not adhere to this routine, indicating a strong commitment to continuous care.

Engagement with Public NCD Clinics and Awareness Initiatives: The survey revealed that 88% of respondents have visited a public NCD clinic at least once, showing a high level of engagement with public health services. However, 12% have never visited these clinics, indicating a gap in outreach or accessibility.

Awareness about government-organized NCD screening and preventive camps is relatively high, with 85% of respondents being aware of such initiatives. Yet, 15% remain unaware, highlighting the need for improved communication and outreach efforts.

Participation in these preventive camps is more moderate, with 53% having attended at least one,

while 47% have not. This suggests that while awareness is high, there may be barriers to participation that need to be addressed.

Community Support and Health Sector Preferences: The role of Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs) is pivotal in the management of NCDs at the community level. The survey indicates that 86% of respondents were visited by an ASHA worker in the past six months, reflecting active community engagement. However, 14% did not receive such visits, suggesting that some areas may require more attention.

When it comes to choosing a healthcare provider, 66% of respondents prefer government services for the treatment of NCDs, while 34% opt for private healthcare. However, when the cost of treatment is removed as a factor, the preference shifts significantly, with 65% favoring private healthcare services and 35% choosing government facilities. This indicates that cost is a significant factor in healthcare decision-making.

Accessibility and Satisfaction with Healthcare Services: Access to healthcare facilities is evenly distributed among the respondents, with 50% living within 5 kilometers of a healthcare center and the other 50% living 5 kilometers or more away. This balance suggests that while half of the population has convenient access to healthcare, the other half may face challenges in reaching services.

Regular access to medicines from public NCD clinics remains a concern, as only 53% of respondents report receiving their medications consistently. The remaining 47% face difficulties in obtaining their necessary medications, which could hinder effective disease management.

Insurance coverage is another important factor, with 65% of respondents having some form of insurance. This coverage likely eases the financial burden of treatment, while the 35% without

insurance may face financial barriers to accessing care.

Despite these challenges, a significant majority of respondents are satisfied with their current

treatment services. 78% expressed satisfaction, while 22% are not satisfied. This high satisfaction rate suggests that the healthcare services, whether public or private, are generally meeting the needs of most patients.

Table 2: Understanding Patient Behavior and Preferences in Managing Non-Communicable Diseases

Variable	Category	Number	Percentage
Taking medication for their illness	Yes	98	98%
	No	2	2%
Visiting a health care center regularly(every 1 month)	Yes	96	96%
	No	4	4%
Visited a public NCD clinic at least once	Yes	88	88%
	No	12	12%
Awareness about NCD Screening and preventive camps organized by government	Aware	85	85 %
	Not aware	15	15%
Participated in government organized preventive camps	Yes	53	53%
	No	47	47%
Visited by an ASHA worker in past 6 months	Yes	86	86%
	No	14	14%
Preferred health service sector for treatment of NCD	Government	66	66%
	Private	34	34%
Preferred health service sector for treatment of NCD if cost of treatment is kept aside	Government	35	35%
	Private	65	65%
Distance from the nearest health care center	<5km	50	50%
	>/=5km	50	50%
Getting medicines regularly from public NCD clinics	Yes	35	53%
	No	31	47%
Having an insurance coverage	Yes	65	65%
	No	35	35%
Satisfied by current treatment service	Yes	78	78%
	No	22	22%

Key Factors Influencing Utilization of Government NCD Services: The current study identified that 66% preferred government health sector for treatment of NCDs.

The utilization of government services for managing non-communicable diseases (NCDs) is significantly influenced by various socio-demographic factors, as highlighted in this study. Education plays a crucial role, with individuals holding higher secondary education levels showing the highest utilization rate of government services at 37%. In contrast, those with only primary education have a much lower utilization rate of 2%. This difference, supported by a strong statistical significance (Chi-square = 35.87, $p = 0.000$), indicates that higher educational attainment may lead to better awareness and access to these services.

Occupation also significantly impacts the use of government NCD services. The study found that semiskilled workers have the highest utilization rate at 36%, while those who are unemployed or in skilled professions have much lower rates, at 7% and 1%, respectively. This relationship, with a Chi-

square value of 40.406 and a p -value of 0.000, suggests that the nature of one's employment can influence their reliance on government healthcare services.

Interestingly, socioeconomic status did not show a significant impact on the utilization of these services. While the middle class had the highest usage at 25%, followed by the lower middle and upper middle classes at 19% and 21% respectively, the upper class had the lowest at 1%. However, the Chi-square value of 1.64 and a p -value of 0.650 indicate no statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and service utilization.

Proximity to healthcare centers was found to be a significant factor, with individuals living more than 5 kilometers away from a healthcare center utilizing government services more frequently (38%) than those living closer (28%). The statistical significance here (Chi-square = 16.501, $p = 0.011$) suggests that those in more remote areas may have fewer alternatives and therefore rely more on government services.

Visits from Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHA) also play a critical role, as individuals who were visited by an ASHA worker had a much higher utilization rate of government services (64%) compared to those who were not visited (2%). This strong association (Chi-square = 19.40, $p = 0.000$) underscores the importance of community health workers in connecting people to available healthcare services.

The study also examined whether the availability of medicines affects service utilization and found no significant association, as the utilization rates were similar between those who had access to medicines (35%) and those who did not (31%). The lack of statistical significance (Chi-square = 0.412, $p = 0.520$) suggests that other factors may be more influential in determining service utilization.

Finally, insurance coverage was identified as a significant factor, with individuals both with and

without insurance showing equal utilization rates (33%). The strong association here (Chi-square = 19.198, $p = 0.000$) indicates that insurance status can influence the decision to use government services, possibly due to the perceived reliability or lower out-of-pocket costs.

In conclusion, this study highlights that education, occupation, proximity to healthcare centers, and ASHA worker visits are key determinants of government NCD service utilization. Although socioeconomic status and the availability of medicines did not show a significant impact, these findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions, such as community outreach and education, to enhance access to and the effectiveness of government healthcare services for managing NCDs.

Table 3: Factors affecting health care service utilization among study population (n=100)

		Percentage of study population utilizing government NCD services	Pearson chi square value	Asymptotic significance (p) value
Highest level of education	Primary	2	35.87	0.0001
	Secondary	8		
	Higher secondary	37		
	Graduate	9		
	Post graduate	0		
Occupation	Unemployed	7	40.406	0.0001
	Unskilled	13		
	Semiskilled	36		
	Skilled	1		
	Professional	9		
Socioeconomic status	Lower middle class	19	1.64	0.650
	Middle class	25		
	Upper middle class	21		
	Upper class	1		
Distance from the nearest health care center	<5km	28	16.501	0.011
	>5km	38		
Visited by ASHA worker	Yes	64	19.40	0.000
	No	2		
Availability of medicines	Yes	35	0.412	0.520
	No	31		
Insurance coverage	Yes	33	19.198	0.000
	No	33		

Discussion

The findings from the current survey provide a comprehensive view of the utilization of non-communicable disease (NCD) services across various settings, shedding light on the patterns and factors influencing healthcare access.

Utilization Rates and Preferences: The survey reveals that 66% of the study population prefers public NCD clinics, which is notably higher

compared to the 34.67% utilization reported in Kasaragod, Kerala by C. K. Bhagyalakshmi and Prakash Babu Kodali [3]. However, the preference for private healthcare services rises to 65% when the cost is not considered, suggesting that affordability significantly influences healthcare choices. This contrasts with a higher overall utilization rate of 55.3% for NCD services from upgraded primary care centers in Kerala, as reported by Resmi Mathew and Jeby J. Olickal [4].

Factors Influencing Utilization: Several factors influencing NCD service utilization have been identified in different studies. Devarshi Bhattacharyya et al. found significant factors to include residence, health insurance, provider preference, income, education, waiting time, and distance to the health center, with an outpatient utilization rate of 74.1% [5]. Similarly, our study highlights the significant impact of educational status, occupation, distance to healthcare centers, visits by healthcare workers, and insurance coverage on the choice of healthcare facilities.

Sanghamitra Pati et al. reported a positive association between the number of NCDs and healthcare utilization for both outpatient and inpatient services [6], emphasizing that higher NCD burden may drive increased service use. This is consistent with our finding that individuals with greater healthcare needs may rely more on government services, particularly when facing financial constraints.

Awareness and Accessibility: Awareness and accessibility issues also play a crucial role. Dr. Oommen P. Mathew's study indicated that nearly 58% of individuals had never visited a facility for NCD screening or treatment, with higher awareness observed among younger patients, females, those with secondary or lower education, and individuals from below-poverty-line (BPL) families [7]. In contrast, our survey found that 85% of participants were aware of government-organized NCD screening and preventive camps, yet only 53% attended them. This suggests a gap between awareness and actual service utilization, possibly due to accessibility issues or perceived inadequacies of the services.

Government Facility Utilization: Devi Nair and Krishnanunni Raveendran's study showed that 60.5% of NCD respondents used government facilities regardless of socioeconomic status [8]. This is slightly lower than the 66% preference for public NCD clinics observed in our survey, highlighting a consistent trend of reliance on government services for NCD management across different studies.

In contrast, a study on the NPCDCS in Kerala found that only 40.9% of individuals diagnosed with NCDs utilized the program's services, suggesting that infrastructure and service availability may be inadequate [9]. This aligns with findings from a study in Dakshina Kannada district, Karnataka, which reported that while health promotion activities were well-prepared, there were deficiencies in resources and infrastructure for NCD management [10].

Care-Seeking Practices: Finally, Nilanjan Bhor's study on care-seeking practices in a low-income neighborhood highlighted issues such as delayed

diagnosis and failure to meet treatment goals [11]. This underscores the importance of timely and effective screening and treatment, which may be compromised by barriers such as inadequate infrastructure and long wait times.

In summary, while the survey aligns with several findings from previous research regarding the utilization of public NCD services, it also highlights critical areas for improvement, such as accessibility, infrastructure, and the alignment between awareness and utilization. Addressing these factors through targeted interventions can enhance the effectiveness of NCD management programs and improve overall healthcare outcomes.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing the utilization of government non-communicable disease (NCD) services. The findings highlight that while a significant portion of the population engages with public NCD clinics, preferences shift markedly towards private healthcare when the cost of treatment is not a consideration. Key determinants of healthcare service utilization include educational attainment, occupation, proximity to healthcare centers, visits by healthcare workers, and insurance coverage.

Individuals with higher education and those in skilled or professional jobs tend to favor private healthcare, while those living closer to public health centers, visited by ASHA workers, or without insurance are more likely to rely on government services. These results underscore the importance of addressing barriers to public healthcare access and improving the quality and availability of services to meet the needs of diverse populations.

The study also emphasizes the critical role of community health workers in increasing awareness and facilitating access to public health programs. Overall, these findings suggest that targeted interventions are necessary to enhance the effectiveness and reach of government NCD services, particularly in underserved communities. By addressing these factors, public health strategies can be better tailored to improve healthcare outcomes and equity in NCD management.

Ethics approval and consent to participate:

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Research Committee of MES Medical College, Perinthalmanna. Written informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study.

List of abbreviations:

1. NCDs - non-communicable diseases
2. NCD - Non-communicable disease (used as both singular and plural)

3. Jamovi - Statistical software (version mentioned: 2.3)
4. p - Probability value (commonly used in statistical tests)
5. q - Complementary probability value ($q = 100 - p$)
6. d - Absolute error or precision in the sample size formula
7. Z - Z-score (related to confidence intervals in statistics)
8. ASHA - Accredited Social Health Activist
9. CHC - Community Health Center
10. PHC - Primary Health Center
11. THQH - Taluk Headquarters Hospital
12. DH - District Hospital
13. BPL - Below Poverty Line
14. HTN - Hypertension
15. DM - Diabetes Mellitus
16. CAD - Coronary Artery Disease
17. NPCDCS - National Programme for Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Diseases and Stroke.

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Authors' Contributions: AR analyzed the interpreted the patient data and done the statistical analysis and was major contributor in writing the manuscript. AP was involved in collecting the data and in conceiving the research. LKK and AS has helped in preparing the manuscript while MS was involved in conceptualization and protocol preparation of the study. All other authors were involved in data collection and data entry. All authors read and approved the final manuscript

References

1. Noncommunicable diseases [Internet]. Who.int. [cited 2024 Aug 28]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>
2. Hay SI, Abdulkader RS, Afshin A, Agarwal SK, Aggarwal AN, Aggarwal R, et al. India: Health of the nation's states - the India state-level disease burden initiative. Indian Council of Medical Research; 2017.
3. Bhagyalakshmi CK, Kodali PB. Utilization of noncommunicable disease services provided by public health facilities in Kasaragod, Kerala. Archives of Medicine and Health Sciences. 2019 Jan 1;7(1):18-24.
4. Mathew R, Olickal JJ. Noncommunicable Disease Service Utilization from the Upgraded Primary Care Centers: A Cross-Sectional Study from Kerala, India. *drugs*. 2023 Oct 11; 6:7.
5. Bhattacharyya D, Pattanshetty SM, Duttagupta C. A cross-sectional study to identify the factors associated with utilisation of healthcare for non-communicable diseases in a southern part of India. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 2017 Jan 1;6(1):96-101.
6. Pati S, Agrawal S, Swain S, Lee JT, Vellakkal S, Hussain MA, Millett C. Non communicable disease multimorbidity and associated health care utilization and expenditures in India: cross-sectional study. *BMC health services research*. 2014 Dec; 14:1-9.
7. Mathew OP, Sachin KV. A study on NCD intervention programme. Thiruvananthapuram: University of Kerala; 2018. PRC Report Series 2018-6.
8. Nair D, Raveendran K. Non-communicable diseases and public health facility utilization: A study in rural Kerala. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2020 Jun; 7:2254-61.
9. Raj U, Akshaya KM, Bhargava M. Are primary health centers prepared for noncommunicable disease management? A facility-based mapping of gaps in coastal Karnataka, India. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*. 2021 Jan 1;46(1):130-3.
10. Shammy R. A study on utilization of diagnostic and therapeutic services of National Program for Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes and Cardiovascular Diseases and Stroke (NPCDCS) from primary health care institutions in Pathanamthitta District (Doctoral dissertation, SCTIMST).
11. Bhor N. Care-seeking practices for non-communicable chronic conditions in a low-income neighborhood in Southern India. *PLOS Global Public Health*. 2023 Jun 29;3(6):e002074.